

Examining the Role of Cultural Influences on Women Entrepreneurs in Real Estate Services in Limpopo, South Africa

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The complex relationship between culture and women entrepreneurs performance in the real estate services industry is examined in this paper. It explores how cultural norms, beliefs, and practices affect women's participation and performance in the industry. Using a qualitative research design, the study involved in-depth interviews with eighteen women entrepreneurs operating in the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province. Thematic analysis of the data revealed that while patriarchal norms, gender-based expectations, and restrictions on women's mobility continue to constrain entrepreneurial advancement, supportive family structures, social networks, and community-driven cultural values such as *Ubuntu* serve as crucial enablers. The findings highlight that women entrepreneurs often navigate a dual landscape of cultural barriers and facilitators, balancing traditional family roles with professional ambitions. Economic limitations, limited mentorship opportunities, and restricted access to finance were also found to hinder growth in the sector. Conversely, cultural adaptability, education, and collective empowerment initiatives were identified as potential catalysts for success. The paper concludes that culture functions as both a challenge and an opportunity, influencing women's entrepreneurial outcomes through its evolving social context. It recommends targeted policy interventions, financial inclusion strategies, and community sensitisation programmes to foster gender equity and sustainable entrepreneurship in the real estate sector, while suggesting further research into intersectional and regional cultural influences on women's enterprise development.

Keywords: Women entrepreneurs, culture, real estate industry and inclusive entrepreneurship

Cultural values play a dual role in shaping women's entrepreneurial experiences. Research by Khosa and Kalitanyi (2021) observes that deeply ingrained gender stereotypes in African nations frequently force women into the unorganised sector and restrict their access to mentorship and funding. Nonetheless, cultural ideas like *Ubuntu* have been recognised for creating networks of support and improving relational capital, which are crucial for industries like real estate (Dube, 2023). In addition, studies by Iwu, Kapondoro, Twum-Darko, and Tengeh (2020) and Nyoni (2021) suggest that changing gender views and cultural adaptability can have a big impact on company results. Even while patriarchal constraints are still common in some places, more women are pursuing business endeavours thanks to changes in cultural views and improved access to media and education. Support from family and spouses has frequently been emphasised as crucial cultural facilitators

(Mokoena, 2022; Akinbinu & Oluwatobi, 2020).

It is commonly acknowledged that entrepreneurship is a key factor in innovation, economic progress, and the fight against poverty (Fatoki, 2021; Akinbinu & Oluwatobi, 2020). However, sociocultural factors have a significant impact on women's entrepreneurial success, especially in underdeveloped nations (Fatoki, 2021; Akinbinu & Oluwatobi, 2020). Autonomy, social networking, and a great deal of fieldwork are all necessary in the difficult real estate profession. Therefore, cultural norms regarding gender roles, mobility, and work-life balance may provide unique difficulties for women in this industry (Chitsike, 2022; Mahlalela & Msimango-Galawe, 2023). Despite advancements in gender equality around the world, patriarchal customs and cultural expectations still prevent women from engaging in entrepreneurship (World Economic Forum, 2023).

Furthermore, recent studies highlight how women's self-perception and business activities are shaped by their religious and traditional views (Musallam & Kamarudin, 2021; Nugroho, Setyawan, & Yunita, 2023). Although such views have the potential to strengthen constrictive conventions, they can also promote virtues like honesty, tenacity, and civic duty that promote the long-term viability of businesses (Tshabalala, 2021; Zulu & Mncayi, 2020).

Challenges Faced by Women Entrepreneurs in Real Estate Services

Women entrepreneurs in the real estate services industry face a range of challenges rooted in cultural, structural, and economic factors. One of the most persistent barriers is the influence of traditional gender roles and societal expectations, which often confine women

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to domestic responsibilities and limit their ability to fully participate in entrepreneurial activities (Botha & Bushe, 2022; Mkhize, 2021). Many women struggle to balance business demands with family obligations, leading to time constraints and reduced networking opportunities. Additionally, mobility restrictions, driven by safety concerns and cultural norms discouraging independent travel, further hinder their ability to meet clients, attend training, or explore new markets (Ebewo, Schultz, & Mmako, 2025; Competition Commission South Africa, 2023; Duri, McKay, & Gunter, 2025).

Despite growing awareness and changing cultural attitudes, women in real estate still contend with systemic discrimination and lack of recognition. These challenges collectively impede their progress, limiting their competitiveness and representation in leadership roles. Addressing these barriers requires coordinated policy action, capacity-building initiatives, and the creation of inclusive support systems that empower women to thrive within the real estate sector.

Review of Literature

According to Khumalo and Zondo (2021), culture is a system of shared ideals, standards, and beliefs that sets one nation's citizens apart from another. Furthermore, Khumalo and Zondo (2021) indicate that culture encompasses lifestyles developed by a community and passed down from one generation to the next. For the purpose of this paper, Guelich, Bullough, Manolova, and Schjoedt's (2021) definition is adopted, which states that culture might be seen as a "rich complex of meanings, beliefs, practices, symbols, norms and values prevalent among people in a society".

People in Asian cultures are supposed to avoid "losing one's face". This term indicates that they are not risk-averse in this cultural setting because they do not want to make mistakes, and they lack confidence in their abilities because losing face entails losing one's reputation in that culture. Additionally, Taiwan's highly rated cultural component, "uncertainty avoidance", of such unpleasant, awkward, dangerous, or hazardous circumstances (Schröder, Bobek, & Horvat, 2021).

A person's decision to become an entrepreneur by starting a business is greatly influenced by social and cultural factors. Since maintaining one's face is ingrained in Asian culture identity (Tan & Li, 2023) losing it is a sign of losing the respect of others. This social norm may be the reason why many Asians are often afraid of failing. They do not want to jeopardise their standing and reputation within society that they have worked so hard to build. Additionally, it is frequently the case that others, such as staff, are upholding the concept of 'face'. Losing face is typically associated with shame, an emotion that makes people feel the need to hide. This practice frequently results in social isolation, alienation and a loss of authority (Tan & Li, 2023).

According to Adom and Anambane (2020), cultural perceptions of gender and entrepreneurship have a detrimental effect on women entrepreneurs. One of the main causes of gender disparity in emerging nations is the prevalence of cultural customs that exacerbate partiality towards men (Mkhize, 2023; Chinomona & Maziriri, 2022). Cultural-cognitive factors have a significant impact on entrepreneurship and need special consideration because culture is inherently difficult to alter. This specific factor is probably going to be the most difficult to handle for policymakers in countries such as Tanzania (Nziku & Henry, 2021)

Women prefer to remain within cultural bounds, prioritising familial commitment bonds, traditional culture or social pressure, even when they face and have to overcome obstacles to achieve their entrepreneurial aspirations (Dewitt, Jafari-Sadeghi, Sukumar, Aruvanahalli Nagaraju, Sadraei, & Li, 2023). In this regard, various reviewed research studies examined the robust practice to which the majority of Albanians adhere that prohibited women from engaging in the same activities as males, including entrepreneurship (Ahmetaj, Kruja, & Hysa, 2023).

Culture appears to be the most pervasive and cumbersome type of enslavement, and it takes many different forms. The most evident is how deeply ingrained male authority is in the patriarchy that creates the world through their constant battle to control, coerce, dictate, and impose their will on women (Ojediran & Anderson, 2020). Although women's entrepreneurial activity and empowerment are severely restricted in Islamic Pakistan by gender inequality, systematic enslavement of women, and underlying societal systems. Despite the stark differences between the nations in East Asia and the Pacific, culture, customs, and religion are vital to women's entrepreneurship and empowerment (Ojediran & Anderson, 2020).

Relevance of the Study

The study is highly relevant as it contributes to the growing discourse on gender, culture, and entrepreneurship within the South African context, particularly in the real estate services sector a field historically dominated by men. By examining how cultural norms, beliefs, and practices influence women's entrepreneurial success, the research provides critical insights into the socio-cultural dynamics that either constrain or empower female entrepreneurs. Understanding these dynamics is essential for designing interventions that promote gender equity and inclusive economic participation.

Furthermore, the study addresses a significant gap in existing literature by focusing on women entrepreneurs in the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province, where cultural traditions and community expectations remain deeply embedded in daily life. It highlights how factors such as family support, social capital, and traditional values can serve as both barriers and facilitators to business success. The findings not only illuminate the lived experiences of women in a specific regional context but also offer transferable lessons for other developing economies facing similar cultural and structural challenges.

Objective of the Study

To examine the relationship between culture and the success of women entrepreneurs in real estate services.

Hypothesis of the study

There is a significant relationship between cultural factors and the success of women entrepreneurs in the real estate services industry in the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province.

Method

Participants

The study included eighteen (18) women entrepreneurs in the real estate services sector within the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province, with ages ranging from 18 to over 59 years. Engagement was highest among participants aged 40-48, followed by notable

involvement from the 29-38 group. The youngest group (18-28) showed the lowest participation, while the 49-58 and 59+ groups, though moderately to lightly engaged, were still consistently represented. These participants were selected through a convenient sampling method to ensure accessibility and relevance to the research objectives. All participants were actively involved in real estate activities such as property sales, rentals, and management. They represented diverse demographic backgrounds in terms of age, education, and marital status, allowing for a rich and varied understanding of their entrepreneurial experiences. The majority of participants were Black women, reflecting the demographic composition of the district. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained prior to data collection. Each participant engaged in a one-hour face-to-face interview conducted in a private and comfortable setting to ensure confidentiality and openness in sharing experiences.

Research Design

The study employed a qualitative research design to explore the relationship between culture and the success of women entrepreneurs in the real estate services sector within the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province. This design was chosen because it allows for an in-depth understanding of participants' experiences, perceptions, and the meanings they attach to cultural influences on their entrepreneurial activities. Through this approach, the researcher was able to capture the complex social and cultural contexts that shape women's participation and success in the industry.

Data were collected through structured face-to-face interviews with eighteen women entrepreneurs. The qualitative design enabled the use of open-ended questions, allowing participants to express their views freely and in detail. Thematic analysis was employed to identify recurring patterns, themes, and sub-themes from the responses, providing rich insights into the influence of cultural values, gender roles, and social expectations on women's entrepreneurial journeys. This design was particularly suitable for uncovering underlying social dynamics that quantitative methods might overlook.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the study, including informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. The qualitative research design thus provided a comprehensive and context-sensitive understanding of how cultural factors affect women's entrepreneurial success in the real estate services industry.

Measures

The primary instrument used for data collection in this study was a structured interview guide developed by the researcher. The interview guide consisted of open-ended questions designed to elicit detailed responses about participants' experiences, perceptions, and challenges related to the influence of culture on their entrepreneurial success in the real estate services sector. The instrument focused on key areas such as cultural practices, gender roles, belief systems, family and community support, access to financial and professional networks, and barriers to business growth.

The structured interview guide was carefully constructed to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study's objectives. It allowed flexibility for participants to elaborate on their experiences, thereby enabling the researcher to probe further where necessary to gain deeper insights. In addition to the interview guide,

a voice recorder was used (with participants' consent) to accurately capture responses for transcription and analysis, ensuring data validity and reliability. Field notes were also taken during each interview to record non-verbal cues, emotional expressions, and contextual details that enriched the interpretation of the data.

Overall, the combination of the structured interview guide, audio recordings, and field notes provided a comprehensive and reliable means of collecting qualitative data for the study, ensuring that participants' perspectives were authentically represented and adequately analysed.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the structured interviews were analysed using thematic analysis, a qualitative method suitable for identifying, analysing, and interpreting patterns of meaning within textual data. After all interviews were completed, the audio recordings were transcribed verbatim to ensure the accuracy and integrity of participants' responses. The research team then thoroughly read the transcripts several times to become familiar with the data and to identify recurring ideas and significant statements related to cultural influences on women's entrepreneurial success. The coding process involved grouping similar responses into categories that reflected key concepts and experiences shared by the participants. From these categories, themes and sub-themes were developed to represent the major factors affecting women entrepreneurs in the real estate services sector. Thematic analysis thus provided a rich and nuanced understanding of how culture shapes the experiences and success of women entrepreneurs in the Capricorn District's real estate sector.

Results and Discussion

The purpose of the paper was to examine the relationship between culture and the success of women entrepreneurs in real estate services in Capricorn, Limpopo Province, South Africa. The paper's findings are analysed according to the themes. The sub-themes that arose from the data analysis of individual structured interviews performed with 18 participants. The primary aim of the paper was to furnish critical reasoning and present the outcomes. The results presentation commences with participants' biographical information, succeeded by their responses according to the research question:

What is the relationship between culture and the success of women entrepreneurs in real estate services?

This paper involved individual, face-to-face interviews with 18 women entrepreneurs in the real estate sector. Appointments were scheduled with them, and they were interviewed at locations of their preference, specifically their offices. The demographic features of the participants are delineated in tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 below:

Table 1

Age Group of the Participants

Age Group	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
18-28	1	5.56%	5.56%
29-38	5	27.78%	33.34%
39-48	7	38.89%	72.23%
49-58	4	22.22%	94.45%
>59	1	5.56%	100%
Total	18	100%	

Age Group

Table 1 shows the results according to the participants' age groups. The participants were between the ages of 18 and over 59, and the age group of 39 to 48 showed the highest level of engagement, suggesting that this group is probably the main audience or most interested in the subject. There is a notable level of engagement within the 29-38 age group. The youngest age group's low involvement (18-28 years old) suggests that outreach may have been lacking or that younger individuals may not have been interested. Although their engagement is moderate to low, the 49-58 and >59 age groups are nevertheless somewhat noticeable. level of education, as seen in Table 2.

Table 2

Educational Level of the Participants

Educational Level	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
Matric	5	27.78%	27.78%
Diploma	7	38.89%	66.67%
Degree	4	22.22%	88.89%
Honours	1	5.56%	94.44%
Masters and above	1	5.56%	100%
Total	18	100%	

Educational Level

The participants' educational attainment is displayed in Table 2. There were no cases of people who had never gone to school; all participants had some degree of formal education. The most common certification is a diploma, which suggests that access to or demand for vocational or technical training is high. One of the most common educational outcomes is matriculation, as many respondents choose not to pursue further education. Participation in post-diploma higher education has significantly decreased. Only one respondent has earned honours or a master's degree or higher, which may indicate limited access to or interest in pursuing postgraduate studies. Participants' race, as indicated by the results in Table 3:

Table 3

Race of the Participants

Race	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
Black	12	66.67%	66.67%
White	5	27.78%	94.44%
Coloured	0	0%	94.44%
Indian	1	5.56%	100%
Other	0	0%	100%
Total	18	100%	

Race

The racial makeup of the participants is displayed in Table 3. With a total of twelve responses, the Black racial group obtained the most responses of any group interviewed. There were four answers from the White racial group. There were no responses from the coloured racial category. There was only one response and very little interaction between the Indian and other racial groups. Across all responses, Black and White individuals showed the highest levels of engagement. However, White participants showed focused reactions in specific domains, while Black participants showed a wide variety

of responses. The following Table 4 shows the participants' marital status:

Table 4

Marital Status of the Participants

Marital Status	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
Married	10	55.56%	5.56%
Single	6	33.33%	33.34%
Widow	2	11.11%	72.23%
Divorced	0	0%	94.45%
Separated	0	0%	100%
Total	18	100	

Marital Status

The participants' marital status is displayed in Table 4. Nine out of sixteen participants said that they were married, making it the most common marital status among responses. With five responses, single people made up the second-largest cohort. With only two responses, widowed people were the least represented group in the recorded responses. For the "Divorced" and "Separated" statuses, no responses were recorded, indicating that these statuses were either completely absent or only partially represented in the sample. According to the paper's findings, married people make up the majority of respondents (55.6%), which indicates a sizable percentage in committed, long-term relationships. Single people make up 33.3% of the population, which may include younger or single people.

Themes Related to the Relationship between Culture and Success of Women Entrepreneurs in Real Estate Services

The analysis of the interview data identified theme and sub-themes related to the relationship between culture and success of women entrepreneurs in real estate services. Table 5 with the theme and sub-themes are discussed below:

Table 5

Theme and Sub-themes

Main Theme	Sub-Theme
1. Cultural Barriers to Women's Success in Real Estate	1.1. Gender Roles and Cultural Expectations
	1.2. Restrictions on Women's Mobility
	1.3. Gender-Based Restrictions
	1.4. Economic Limitations

Main Theme: Cultural Barriers to Women's Success in Real Estate

The paper's findings reveal that cultural obstacles continue to pose a substantial hindrance to women's success in the real estate market within the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province. Numerous participants recounted situations illustrating how conventional gender roles, racial prejudices, and societal expectations obstruct their business endeavours. These experiences align with recent studies showing that women in male-dominated sectors continue to encounter discriminatory attitudes, restricted access to networks, and culturally embedded expectations that prioritise domestic responsibilities over professional pursuits (Mtsweni & Combrink, 2023; Ebewo, Schultz, & Mmako, 2025).

For instance, Participant 16 expressed frustration with systemic exclusion, stating, “*White people are not supporting in the industry. Trial and error,*” suggesting racial and possibly gender-based discrimination that limits support and access to essential business networks. This is consistent with findings by Sebola (2024) who notes that racialised market structures and historical inequalities continue to marginalise Black women entrepreneurs in South Africa.

Participant 2 further emphasized the burden of caregiving roles traditionally assigned to women, stating that support is needed for “*women with family-related issues in order to make a success of the business (sick children, sports days or events),*” highlighting the tension between cultural expectations and business obligations. Similar patterns have been observed in recent studies reporting that traditional gender roles and disproportionate household responsibilities limit women's availability for client meetings, training, and market expansion activities (Chinomona & Maziriri, 2022; Mkhize, 2023).

Overall, the findings underscore the simultaneous influence of cultural norms and institutional exclusion on women's participation in the real estate sector. Despite certain advancements, enduring cultural and systemic constraints continue to disadvantage women, signalling the need for interventions that address not only entrepreneurial skills but also societal attitudes and structural inequalities.

Sub-theme: Gender Roles and Cultural Expectations

The paper's findings indicate that gender norms and cultural expectations significantly shape the entrepreneurial experiences of women in the real estate sector in the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province. Numerous interviewees emphasised that conventional family obligations and cultural perceptions of women's roles hinder their capacity to fully participate in economic activities. These findings align with recent research showing that women entrepreneurs in South Africa continue to carry a disproportionate burden of caregiving responsibilities, which reduces their business engagement and limits their mobility and professional development (Mkhize, 2023; Chinomona & Maziriri, 2022).

For example, Participant 2 emphasized the need for both institutional and familial support to help women balance their entrepreneurial ambitions with caregiving duties, noting that support is essential “to support women with family-related issues in order to make a success of the business (sick children, sports days or events).” This mirrors findings by Ebewo, Schultz, and Mmako (2025), who report that household obligations often force women entrepreneurs to prioritise family over opportunity-seeking activities. Similarly, Participant 14 discussed the importance of having motivational speakers and emotional support systems in place, adding that organisations should be “understanding when there is a sick child,” underscoring the constant negotiation women must navigate between familial responsibilities and professional demands. Comparable patterns have been documented in other studies, which highlight that emotional support, mentorship, and flexible working environments are crucial for enhancing women's entrepreneurial participation (Mtsweni & Combrink, 2023).

Overall, the paper highlights that cultural expectations regarding women's domestic and social responsibilities continue to be a substantial barrier to their success in the real estate sector in the Capricorn District. Confronting these issues requires a multifaceted strategy that includes policy endorsement, community education,

and improved exposure, mentorship, and support systems for women entrepreneurs. These approaches align with scholarly recommendations for addressing gendered constraints and promoting an equitable business environment for women (Sebola, 2024).

Sub-theme: Restrictions on Women's Mobility

The paper revealed that limitations on women's movement continue to be a substantial obstacle to entrepreneurial achievement in the real estate industry in the Capricorn District. Participants noted that safety concerns, familial obligations, and cultural norms frequently restrict their ability to travel for business, attend meetings, or participate in networking outside conventional working hours. These constraints are not only logistical but also deeply rooted in gendered expectations, reflecting broader societal patterns observed in recent literature (Duri, McKay, & Gunter, 2025; Mkhize, 2023).

Participant 8 emphasized the need for enhanced safety measures, stating that “*women safety measures are needed in the business... safety measures in place and screening of potential clients and meeting place to be the office.*” This concern is consistent with findings by Duri et al. (2025) who demonstrate that women in South Africa often avoid certain locations or times of travel due to fear of harassment or violence, which limits their economic mobility.

Similarly, Participant 2 highlighted the challenge of balancing mobility with family responsibilities, noting that support for “*family-related issues... is critical for success.*” This aligns with research showing that women's mobility is frequently restricted by caregiving duties, which reduce the time and flexibility required for entrepreneurial activities (Chinomona & Maziriri, 2022; Mtsweni & Combrink, 2023). These studies suggest that domestic responsibilities, combined with cultural expectations that prioritise women's presence in the home, continue to limit women's ability to pursue opportunities that require travel or extended working hours.

Overall, the findings underscore how mobility constraints shaped by safety fears, cultural norms, and domestic responsibilities act as significant barriers to women's entrepreneurial participation in the real estate sector. Addressing these issues requires not only improved security systems and professional structures but also broader societal shifts toward recognising and redistributing caregiving responsibilities (Ebewo, Schultz, & Mmako, 2025).

Sub-theme: Gender-Based Restrictions

The paper's findings indicate that gender-based constraints continue to pose a significant obstacle for women entrepreneurs in the real estate services sector within the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province. Participants identified preconceptions, unequal access to opportunities, and insufficient support from male colleagues as barriers impeding their full engagement and advancement in the industry. These challenges manifest in nuanced but pervasive ways, such as being undervalued by clients, denied guidance by male colleagues, or excluded from elite corporate networks, reflecting patterns observed in recent research on women in male-dominated sectors (Mtsweni & Combrink, 2023; Sebola, 2024).

Participant 14 reflected on this dynamic, stating: “*Self-taught experience and asking around. White people are not supporting in the industry. Trial and error.*” This highlights intersectional barriers both racial and gendered that limit access to mentorship and support for Black women in the real estate sector. These experiences align with findings by Chinomona and Maziriri (2022) who reported that

women often face structural exclusion in professional networks, particularly in industries historically dominated by men and racial hierarchies.

Participant 6 echoed a similar sentiment: *“Being in the business of selling meat assisted with experience,”* suggesting a transition into real estate from informal trading due to limited entry points or lack of formal sector support. This reflects broader trends documented by Ebewo, Schultz, and Mmako (2025) who argue that women entrepreneurs frequently leverage informal sector experience to overcome systemic barriers in formal industries, highlighting resilience but also structural inequities that constrain their professional growth.

Overall, these findings emphasize the importance of addressing both gender- and race-based barriers through targeted mentorship programs, inclusive professional networks, and policies that facilitate equitable access to opportunities for women in the real estate sector.

Sub-theme: Economic Limitations

The paper revealed that financial constraints remain a major obstacle to the growth of women entrepreneurs in the real estate services sector in the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province. Participants highlighted challenges such as limited startup capital, restricted access to operating funds, and the high costs associated with ongoing professional development. These financial limitations frequently impede business expansion, reduce competitiveness, and undermine confidence, particularly when pursuing high-value real estate transactions (Chinomona & Maziriri, 2022; Mkhize, 2023).

Many participants emphasised the financial burden associated with obtaining necessary qualifications, promoting their businesses, and securing office spaces. For instance, Participant 10 suggested: *“Offer bursaries for financial assistance,”* indicating a clear link between financial support and access to entrepreneurship education. Participant 7 highlighted the role of subsidized programmes, stating: *“Learnership applications to provide for support,”* reflecting the importance of financial mechanisms to bridge economic gaps. Additionally, Participant 13 commented: *“Provide detailed training and assist with women speaker (motivational speaker) at least once a month. Be supportive of all women and understanding when there is a sick child for example,”* which underscores the intersection of economic and social constraints that disproportionately affect women entrepreneurs (Ebewo, Schultz, & Mmako, 2025; Mtsweni & Combrink, 2023).

These findings are consistent with research indicating that access to finance remains one of the most persistent barriers for women-led enterprises in South Africa, limiting both startup success and long-term sustainability. Policy interventions such as bursaries, subsidized training, and targeted financial support are essential to reduce these disparities and enable women to compete effectively in the real estate sector (Sebola, 2024).

Findings of the Study

The findings of the study revealed a complex relationship between culture and the success of women entrepreneurs in the real estate services sector within the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province. The thematic analysis of the interviews identified that while cultural values and norms play both restrictive and supportive roles, their overall influence significantly shapes women's entrepreneurial

experiences.

The main theme that emerged was Cultural Barriers to Women's Success in Real Estate, which encompassed four key sub-themes: gender roles and cultural expectations, restrictions on women's mobility, gender-based discrimination, and economic limitations. Participants highlighted that traditional gender roles often confine women to domestic responsibilities, making it difficult to balance family duties with business commitments. Many women expressed that societal expectations continue to prioritise caregiving over entrepreneurship, limiting their availability and flexibility in running their businesses.

Mobility restrictions were also a recurring challenge, with participants citing safety concerns, family obligations, and cultural norms discouraging travel or late working hours. Gender-based discrimination was evident in the form of limited mentorship opportunities, exclusion from male-dominated networks, and unequal access to business opportunities. Economic barriers such as lack of funding, high operational costs, and limited access to financial support programmes further constrained women's growth in the sector.

Despite these challenges, the study also found positive cultural influences. Values such as Ubuntu, family support, and community solidarity were identified as facilitators that enhance women's resilience, networking, and business sustainability. These findings underscore the dual nature of culture as both an obstacle and a source of empowerment in shaping the success of women entrepreneurs in real estate services.

Conclusion

The study concludes that culture plays a dual and dynamic role in shaping the entrepreneurial experiences and success of women in the real estate services sector within the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province. While deeply rooted cultural norms and gender expectations continue to present barriers, such as restricted mobility, unequal access to opportunities, and economic limitations, these same cultural foundations can also foster support, collaboration, and resilience. The findings demonstrate that traditional beliefs and societal structures often confine women to domestic and caregiving roles, limiting their time, mobility, and access to professional networks. However, cultural values like *Ubuntu* and strong family support systems can serve as empowering factors that promote trust, social cohesion, and business growth.

The study further reveals that women entrepreneurs navigate these cultural challenges through adaptability, education, and the creation of supportive peer networks. Their success often depends on balancing familial responsibilities with business aspirations, while leveraging cultural and social capital to build credibility within their communities.

Overall, the study underscores that the intersection of culture and entrepreneurship should not be viewed solely as a source of constraint but also as a potential platform for empowerment. For sustainable advancement, it is essential to implement policies and initiatives that address structural and cultural barriers while amplifying the positive cultural values that encourage inclusivity and women's economic participation. By doing so, the real estate sector can become more equitable, diverse, and responsive to the evolving role of women in entrepreneurship.

Recommendations

The study recommends a multifaceted approach to addressing the cultural and structural barriers that affect women entrepreneurs in the real estate services sector. Based on the identified themes, it is essential to promote gender-sensitive policies that support women's equal participation and access to business opportunities. Organisations should implement family-friendly and flexible work arrangements to help women balance entrepreneurial responsibilities with domestic roles, while community awareness programmes should challenge restrictive cultural norms that limit women's progress.

In relation to restrictions on women's mobility, the study highlights the importance of improving safety and logistical support for women operating in the real estate industry. Measures such as verified client systems, secure meeting spaces, and the use of digital platforms for client engagement could help mitigate safety concerns and enhance women's freedom to conduct business activities independently.

Addressing gender-based restrictions requires deliberate efforts to expand mentorship and professional networking opportunities for women. Establishing women-focused mentorship programmes and professional associations can create platforms for sharing knowledge, building confidence, and accessing new business opportunities. Such initiatives would also help counter exclusion from male-dominated networks and challenge discriminatory practices in the sector.

Overall, the study recommends a collaborative effort among government, financial institutions, and community stakeholders to create an enabling environment that recognises both the challenges and opportunities within cultural systems. By leveraging positive cultural values such as *Ubuntu* and strengthening institutional support, women entrepreneurs can achieve greater inclusion, sustainability, and success in the real estate industry.

Limitations of the Study

This study acknowledges several limitations that may have influenced its scope and findings. The research was conducted using a qualitative design with a small sample of eighteen women entrepreneurs from the Capricorn District, Limpopo Province. While this provided in-depth insights, the results cannot be generalised to all women entrepreneurs in South Africa or other regions, as cultural and business contexts may vary. The use of convenient sampling may also have limited the diversity of participants, potentially excluding voices from women with different experiences or backgrounds.

Despite these limitations, the study offers valuable insights into the interplay between culture and women's entrepreneurial success, serving as a foundation for future research to explore the topic across broader contexts and using mixed-method approaches for greater depth and generalisability.

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